

EFFECT OF COMBINED ENVIRONMENTS ON THE FATIGUE OF CARBON FIBER-VINYLESTER COMPOSITES

C.S. Korach*, A. Afshar, H.T. Liao, F.P. Chiang

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Stony Brook University, Stony Brook, NY, USA

* Corresponding author (chad.korach@stonybrook.edu)

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1 Abstract

Fiber reinforced polymer composites are used as facings for foam core sandwich panels and as lightweight structural materials, which can undergo cyclic loading during application. Exposure to outdoor environments subject composites to ultraviolet (UV) and moisture conditions that cause degradation and weakening during service. Here, accelerated aging of carbon fiber-reinforced vinylester composites is performed using UV radiation and condensation to ascertain the effect on fatigue response. Uniaxial cyclic loading is applied to composite coupons after environmental condition exposure, where the effect of environment will be determined by modulus evolution and post-fatiguing three-point bending.

2 Introduction

An important consideration for fiber reinforced polymers (FRPs) used in off-shore and littoral applications is the effect of sea water, which creates a corrosive environment for metallic materials. Sea water immersion conditions of composites have shown deleterious effects to material properties [1-2]. Previously, the combined effects of UV radiation and moisture and sea water [3-4] were shown to cause decreases in fracture strength and mechanical properties for carbon fiber / vinylester composites, as well as chemical degradation. The combined UV and moisture exposure degrades composites through moisture diffusion [5], which can lead to swelling and fiber-matrix de-bonding, and photo-oxidation of the polymer matrix [6]. Combined environments may include operational stresses on composites, where cyclic loading has been shown to cause an increase in degradation. Combining fatigue of composites and environmental

conditions has proven to decrease the strength and stiffness of carbon fiber epoxy composites [7]. The combination of fatigue loading and combined environmental exposures of UV radiation and moisture has not been addressed for vinylester resin composites. In this paper, the effects of the combined loading and environmental conditions on mechanical and chemical properties will be discussed.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1 Composite Materials

All experiments and conditions used carbon-fiber reinforced vinylester unidirectional composite laminates (Graphtek LLC). Composite laminate sheets with nominal thickness of 1.4 mm were machined using a diamond wet saw into samples of 12.5 x 152 mm (width x length) for fatigue and flexural testing with two fiber directions [0°] and [90°]. A typical specimen is shown in Figures 1 and 2.

3.2 Environmental Exposure

An environmental chamber was used to create the exposure conditions. Samples were exposed to 1000 hours of combined accelerated aging before characterization. Combined ultraviolet radiation and condensation conditions were generated in a Q-Lab QUV/se accelerated weathering chamber (see Figures 3 and 4). High temperature moisture conditions simulate hot and humid environments and are created using humidification and forced-air heat in a sealed chamber. UV radiation simulates natural sunlight using fluorescent UVA bulbs at a 340 nm wavelength. Intensity is monitored by real-time UV irradiance sensors, where temperature is controlled

Fig. 1. Unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced vinylester resin matrix composite samples used in this study were machined to 12.5 x 152 mm beams. Fiber orientation is in the transverse direction (short direction of the coupon). Uniaxial loading was applied in the longitudinal direction.

Fig. 2. Cross-section of unidirectional carbon fiber vinylester composite, as-received.

using a forced-air blower. Condensation is provided by water evaporation from a heated tray in the base of the chamber which condenses on the sample surfaces. The samples are placed at a 60 degree angle. An example of the specimen placement within the chamber is shown in Figure 4.

The conditions in the chambers remained constant for the duration of the exposure. The UV radiation and Condensation conditions cycled every 3 hours. For the UV cycle, the UV irradiance was set at 0.6 W/m^2 with a chamber temperature controlled to 60 C. The condensation cycle was set at a temperature of 50 C. Samples were rotated

within the chamber to remove any effects of chamber location. Sample surfaces were rotated every 48 hours to maintain an even degradation process on both surfaces of the composite samples.

Fig. 3. Environmental exposure performed in laboratory chambers, above QUV/se combined Ultraviolet radiation and condensation chamber.

Fig. 4. Sample position within the QUV/se combined Ultraviolet radiation and condensation chamber. Note: samples are rotated away from the UV bulbs to demonstrate location.

3.3 Cyclic Loading

To study the effect of fatigue on the environmental conditioning of composites, cyclic loading was performed on the composite coupons (see Figure 5). An Instron hydraulic loading frame (Instron 8501) was used in a force control arrangement to provide

cyclic loading of the samples. Aluminum tabs were epoxied to the coupon surfaces which were gripped with mechanical locking wedge grips (Instron 2743) for dynamic loading. Tabs prevented stress concentrations and failure near the grips. The ratio of maximum stress versus tensile stress was set to ~0.4. The ratio of the minimum to maximum stress was set at 0.2. The cycling rate was held constant at 5 Hz. Cyclic loading of the coupons was applied for 50,000 cycles for each sample. The samples used first are underwent environmental conditioning and then fatigue loading. Three samples were used for each condition.

During cyclic loading, the tensile modulus is computed using the load cycle and a clip-on extensometer to measure strain. Data is sampled for 1000 cycles and then averaged. The data is collected every ~5000 cycles of the fatigue loading.

Fig. 5. Sample mounted in a uniaxial loading frame to perform cyclic loading fatigue of composite specimens after environmental exposure conditions.

3.4 Mechanical Characterization

Three point bending tests were performed on the composite samples following the ASTM D790 [8] standard using a screw-driven mechanical loading frame (TiraTest 26005) with a 0.5 kN load cell. The

tests determined flexural strength and bending modulus of the composites after cyclic loading was applied to environmentally conditioned specimens. Specimen sizes were 152 x 12.5 x 1.4 mm (L x W x H). Support geometry followed ASTM D790, with the support span set for 60 mm resulting in a span/thickness ratio of ~43. A crosshead rate of 4.25 mm/min. was used to give a strain rate of 0.01 mm/mm/min.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Specimen Weight Changes

As a result of the sample exposure to moisture and photodegradation conditions, the sample mass will change during the exposure duration. The mass of the composite samples were tracked every 48 hours for the environmental chambers. Mass was measured using a precision balance at the end of the UV cycle, such that condensate was not present on the sample surfaces. The results indicate two distinct trends shown in Figure 6: 1) increase in mass at the beginning of exposure; and 2) plateauing of mass increase and a decrease in mass after longer term exposure. The initial increase in mass is attributed to the presence of moisture that diffuses

Fig. 6. Mass change of composite specimens during combined UV-Condensation environmental exposure conditions.

into the composite through condensing water on the samples surfaces. The moisture diffuses directly into the vinylester resin matrix as well as at the interfaces between the fibers and matrix. Photodegradation of the vinylester matrix will lead to oxidation of the vinylester polymer chains, decreasing the material mass. The photo-oxidation process also breaks polymer chain bonds and weakens the resin, which can lead to surface cracking. The decrease in mass after a peak value of ~500 hours for the combined UV cases indicates loss of surface material due to photodegradation. At this point, the moisture diffusion has reached a steady-state and the competing photo-oxidation process of the vinylester leads to a significant material mass loss.

4.2 Surface Morphology

The effects of the environmental exposure on the vinylester resin were characterized by high-resolution microscopy (Keyence VHX-500) to observe surface changes of the composites. Evidence of micro-cracking and matrix erosion for the composites exposed to the combined UV/condensation conditions can be seen in Figure 7. The image shows the high density of microcracks on the sample edges. Previous results have shown similar microcrack formation in epoxy composite resin surfaces after exposure to combined

Fig. 7. Cross-section of unidirectional carbon fiber vinylester composite, after 1000 hours of combined UV-Condensation exposure. Arrows indicate microcracking of the matrix. Scale bar is 50 microns in length.

UV/condensation conditions [7, 9]. In both instances, the resin demonstrated cracking and erosion of the matrix, which is due to the combination of photo-oxidation of the resin and the cyclic presence of condensate which washes photodegradation products.

4.3 Tensile Modulus During Cyclic Loading

During cyclic loading of the 90 degree composite coupons, the transverse tensile modulus of the composites was computed through measurement of the strain by clip-on extensometer. Modulus was computed from the cyclic load data and the strain which were measured simultaneously by data acquisition. Measurements were made at intervals of ~5000 cycles during the 50,000 cycle test duration. Data was collected for 1000 cycles, and then individual slopes of the load cycles and strain response were calculated for 50 cycles taken at 200 cycle intervals. The computed slopes allow direct calculation of the tensile modulus of the specimens, which were then averaged over the 50 values. The averaged modulus values are plotted versus the number of loading cycles in Figure 8 for both the composites exposed to the combined UV/condensation conditions, and unconditioned as-received samples. The modulus of both sample conditions is observed to decrease rapidly with

Fig. 8. Transverse tensile modulus of unidirectional carbon fiber vinylester composites during cyclic loading, for unconditioned virgin specimens and composites that had been exposed to 1000 hours of combined UV-Condensation.

Table 1. Uniaxial transverse modulus of [90°] plies after environmental degradation and cyclic fatigue loading

Undegraded	
<i>Modulus of uniaxial [90°] plies with fatigue (GPa)</i>	
Fatigue level	
0	8.43
0.5	7.76 (-8%)
UV-condensation	
<i>Modulus of uniaxial [90°] plies with fatigue (GPa)</i>	
Fatigue level	
0	7.91 (-6%)
0.5	7.54 (-11%)

Relative changes in parentheses are with respect to undegraded specimens

loading cycles. The rapid decrease is due to damage within the composite, likely at the fiber-matrix interfaces. Though the initial decrease in modulus is largest after the first 50 cycles for the unconditioned specimens, the UV/condensation samples have a more rapid decrease in modulus over the first 5000 to 10,000 cycles. The overall modulus decrease is largest for the UV/Condensation exposed composites when compared to the non-fatigued undegraded specimens (Table 1). The degraded specimen modulus decrease was ~11%, where the undegraded specimens decrease was ~8%. These results demonstrate the importance fatigue may cause in the evolution of combined environmental effects, even for the low fatigue level (0.5) used in these experiments.

4.4 Mechanical Flexural Response

Three point bending tests are used to determine flexural modulus and residual strength by ASTM D790 [8] for the composite samples exposed to 1000 hours of combined UV-Condensation environment and unconditioned as-received. For the non-fatigued

specimens, the exposure conditions showed an insignificant difference in the flexural modulus when compared to the unconditioned specimens, and within experimental error (Figure 9). These results are consistent with previously reported experiments on uniaxial [90°] ply bending modulus after exposure to combined environmental conditions [3-4]. The bending modulus was found to minimally change when the combination of cyclic fatigue loading was introduced. Cyclic loading had no significant effect on the bending modulus (Figure 9). Results showed the residual flexure strength in the [90°] fiber direction demonstrated sensitivity to the UV-Condensation exposure conditions, with both fatigued and non-fatigued specimens decreasing compared to the unconditioned control (Figure 10). The conditions involving the combined UV-Condensation-Fatigue exhibited the most significant reduction in the residual strength, decreasing by 31% compared with the undegraded composite specimens. This strength loss is attributed to a combination of surface micro-cracking observed from optical microscopy and fiber-matrix debonding occurring within the composite structure. The exposure to the UV radiation demonstrates a synergistic degradation effect which leads to a decrease in the composite mechanical strength. Results from the flexural test are summarized in Table 2.

Fig. 9. Bending modulus, tested by three point bending, of unidirectional carbon fiber vinylester composites after cyclic loading, for unconditioned virgin specimens and composites that had been exposed to 1000 hours of combined UV-Condensation.

Fig. 10. Flexural strength, tested by three point bending, of unidirectional carbon fiber vinylester composites after cyclic loading, for unconditioned virgin specimens and composites that had been exposed to 1000 hours of combined UV-Condensation.

Table 2 Measured modulus and residual strength under flexural load of [90°] plies after environmental degradation and cyclic fatigue loading

	Undegraded	UV-condensation
<i>Bending modulus of uniaxial plies with fatigue (GPa)</i>		
Fatigue level		
0	6.79	6.72 (-1%)
0.5	6.57 (-3%)	6.51 (-4%)
<i>Flexural strength of uniaxial plies with fatigue (MPa)</i>		
Fatigue level		
0	103.9	73.8 (-29%)
0.5	96.9 (-7%)	71.4 (-31%)

Relative changes in parentheses are with respect to undegraded specimens

6 Conclusions

This paper focused on the combined effects of cyclic fatigue loading and environmental conditions on the mechanical properties of carbon fiber vinylester

composite laminates. Using cyclic loading conditions and unique environmental exposure capabilities which degrade the composite matrix, the effect of fatigue on aging using combined environments has been determined. Combining fatigue after exposure to a combined environment of UV-Condensation, transverse tensile modulus of [90°] plies is found to have a decrease by 11%. The residual strength of the composite plies is found to decrease by 31% for the samples exposed to UV-Condensation then fatigue. The results demonstrate that composites which have aged due to adverse environmental conditions are more susceptible to fatigue damage resulting in loss of stiffness and residual strength.

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